

THE ADVANTAGES OF USING TECHNICAL MEANS IN INTRODUCING NATURE

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Annatotion: in this article, the advantages of using technical means in introducing Nature. Introducing long-term seasonal changes in nature. opinions are expressed

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Nature is an inexhaustible treasure. Its animate and inanimate nature, diverse flora and fauna serve as a great resource for the proper growth and formation of a young soul, for learning the secrets of nature's events and coming of age. does. The child will be curious. He rejoices and rejoices when he sees the colors around him, the colorful flowers, the flowing waters, the butterflies landing and flying from the flowers, and the birds flying around. The role of the surrounding nature in the growth of the child's mind, in increasing his interest in living and inanimate nature is incomparably great.

We should introduce children to these beautiful landscapes that nature has gifted us, tell them how important each plant and animal of nature is for humans and nature, and teach them, feed them spiritually.

The purpose of introducing children to nature is to educate the young generation in the spirit of loving our motherland, protecting, preserving and increasing its flora and fauna. For this, it is necessary to start introducing children to nature from preschool age.

Accordingly, one of the most important tasks for children's educational institutions and educators working in them is to teach children to see the beauty of nature, to love it, to have a correct understanding of the events that occur in nature, to learn from the wealth created by nature. should consist of education in the spirit of rational use.

The content of introducing children to nature in the pre-school educational institution is highlighted, and directions of formation of knowledge,

skills and skills of work in nature are defined. These requirements can be met only when children are first introduced to the nature of the countries they were born and raised in, because the formation of the knowledge of a preschool-aged child is carried out in the process of direct interaction with the environment that surrounds him. .

Pre-school children's ability to simultaneously distinguish mental and practical actions, observation, acquisition of labor skills is the main condition for their successful acquisition of knowledge.

For example, it is not enough to teach children about what kind of plants there are in the forest, field, meadow; it is necessary to teach children to distinguish and recognize the most common plants according to their characteristic signs.

The main part of the manual is dedicated to the method of introducing children of different age groups to nature. In it, the contents, forms, methods and methods of work in each age group are given according to the seasons.

The issues of introducing children to nature in daily life - work and observation in the corner of nature, purpose-oriented walks are considered in more detail. The main goal for each season is indicated and a list of exercises is given. The activities that teach the educator to observe children, to determine the causes of the connection of events, and the activities designed to generalize and systematize knowledge are described in more detail.

In order to effectively use natural resources, to consciously solve the issues of nature protection, young people who are maturing in the family, community center, school, secondary and higher education institutions, production and public places, learn the secrets of nature and the methods of its proper use. they must get thorough knowledge in all aspects.

In the organization of the lesson process, the use of tests, questions, and posters from handouts is highly effective. The material base plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of education. Demonstration tools are the components of the material base of the natural science cabinet, living nature objects, and the educational-experimental site. The presence of living objects and visual exhibitions allows students to be involved in various independent and practical activities.

The use of various exhibits in nature training requires careful selection and preparation. The German Methodist Listerweg also highly valued the role of demonstration: he said that "a person cannot acquire knowledge in any other way than through demonstration."

Later K.D. Ushinsky developed this theory and justified the importance of demonstration as follows: "However, teach a child five unknown words and he will struggle for a long time in vain: but if you connect with the pace, you will get 20 such questions "he easily assimilates it as if (flying)," he wrote.

In his works, Ushinsky notes that children perceive various words and knowledge through shapes, colors, sizes and sounds, and imaginations are formed. Living beings - all living plants and animals; herbariums, tulums; collections - plants, seeds, fruits, animal collections, minerals, rocks, minerals, soil samples, manure, peat. They can also be prepared by students during group activities and extracurricular activities.

Wet preparations, dry preparations are naturally dried plant and animal parts. They include collections of grain, technical and vegetable crops. Vegetative parts of plants and flower preparations. The skeleton of a river crab belongs to this group. Herbariums of size and size are examples of natural exhibits.

Visual exhibitions. They are sold ready-made in stores, used for self-study and demonstration of sellers. They are prepared as a set. Factories and schools buy the necessary amount.

The following are among the large exhibition tools:

A model is a 3-dimensional display tool that represents the appearance of an object or its individual parts. The model reflects not only the external appearance, but also the internal content, bringing it closer to the natural body. It should also show the principle of operation, for example, a power plant, the movement of the earth around its axis, the operation of a well, a water mill, still life models include models of globes, mountains. It is used to display them.

A miniature view of the globe. Reflects its rotation around its axis, parallel and meridian lines, north, south, west, east sides, lakes, oceans and seas are represented by colored images.

There are also models of internal organs: heart, lung, kidney, flower model, fruit and seed models, some of which children can make themselves. In school conditions, children can make plasticine, paraffin, and cardboard themselves.

A mock-up is an external appearance of an object (color, size, shape) without internal content. Fruits and vegetables related to natural science are vegetables and root fruits. It is released from factories ready-made, that is, it is prepared based on the school program. Dummies are also made with the help of students in the course of class activities.

The application is a volume guide with a one-sided view. Plasticine is made from -mirror particles. The structure of the skin, lungs, kidneys and other

internal organs are prepared in this way and their structures are studied. It is possible to show the circulatory system, breathing, and the structure of the brain.

It is also important to teach how to use a compass and thermometer in elementary grades.

A compass is an instrument used to determine the location of a place. A compass is used in the forest on the outskirts of the city, during trips and walks.

A thermometer is used to determine the expansion of liquid substances with a change in temperature. A thermometer comes in handy when observing the weather, water temperature, and using experiments on plants in science classes.

The screen is a means of sound display. They include educational films, slide films, gram notes, educational shows. These on-screen guides represent events in action. It allows you to see living and non-living creatures in the natural environment, which cannot be seen with the naked eye. Students learn by seeing and hearing.

Still visual aids are very convenient to store and use in the office. To this group:

A) educational pictures;

B) tables;

Animal world - As the temperature drops, the activity of insects begins to slow down. Mosquitoes hide under fallen leaves.

Birds start flying in March. Birds usually fly as soon as food appears for them. The flight of insectivorous birds coincides with the breeding season of insects. Such birds include jays, swallows, and swallows. They build nests in tree hollows.

If you have the opportunity with children, you should observe the swallows making nests on the tops of houses and porches, on the ceilings, and you can tell the children the following riddle.

It's going fast,

He looks from the roof.

Wood - mud sinks,

Basket weaving. (Swallow)

Children should be told that swallows eat various insects that fly in the air. Children should draw attention to the fact that swallows fly low on cloudy days, and fly high on clear days, and explain why.

Children can be allowed to play with baby animals, but it is necessary to explain not to torture them. In front of children, it is necessary to clean the bottom of the animals, give them food, caress them and talk to them, and through this, it is necessary to show an example of caring for animals. You can observe sheep, goats, cows, yearlings grazing with children in pastures and rural conditions. Children should be shown from afar the bleating of a cow, the bleating of a sheep, the bleating of a mare, and the bleating of a goat.

It is necessary to go a little closer and compare a cow and a calf: cows are big, they have a head, a head, and a tail, they drive away flies with their tails, they walk slowly, eat grass, and their calves run.

A sample plan of games and activities on the topics of introducing small group children to the nature of the environment, to love them, to protect them, to take part in their growth and development with their best efforts. it is appropriate to conduct training.

In order to identify and strengthen children's knowledge about nature, it is appropriate to use various didactic and action games.

The educator organizes the children's life in various ways during the day and also carries out educational work.

By taking care of plants and animals, children will gain more knowledge about them, they will acquire labor, skills and abilities to care for them, all of which will increase children's interest in learning more about the secrets of nature. and educates meticulousness and care for them

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